

Abstract

Stroke is the second leading cause of death and disability worldwide. Initiatives to decrease the burden of stroke have largely focused on prevention and acute care strategies. Despite considerable resources and attention, the focus on prevention and acute care has not been successful in changing the clinical trajectory for the majority of stroke patients. While efforts to prevent strokes will continue to have an impact, the total burden of stroke will increase due to the aging population and decreased mortality rates. There is strong evidence for the effectiveness of rehabilitation in better managing stroke and its related disabilities. The time has come to shift the attention in stroke care and research from prevention and cure to a greater focus and investment in the rehabilitation and quality of life of stroke survivors. The rebalancing of stroke care and research initiatives requires a reinvestment in rehabilitation and community reintegration of stroke survivors.

Keywords: acute care; prevention; rehabilitation; stroke.